

Assessing Mathematics Anxiety Level among Early Childhood Care Education Pre-Service Teachers During Computer-Based Versus Paper-and-Pen Examination

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Abstract

The study assessed mathematics anxiety level among Early Childhood Care Education pre-service teachers during computer-based versus paper-and-pen examination. Based on the purpose of the study two research questions guided the study. The population of the study comprised of all the 345 early childhood care education pre-service teachers. The sample size involved all the participants while simple random sampling technique were used to select two groups of pre service teachers namely group one (regular programme) and group two (Evening/ weekend Programme). The instrument used for data collection was adapted Mathematics Anxiety Inventory (MAI) developed by Plake and Parker (1982). Only those pre-service teachers who manifested the three symptoms (physical, psychological and behavioural). Content validity was established, one each from Mathematics education, Curriculum studies, Special education and Measurement and evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach alpha and was found to be 0.85. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The result of the study revealed that, there is high level of mathematics anxiety among Early Childhood Care Education pre-service teachers during computer-based than the paper-and-pen examination and there are several factors that cause mathematics anxiety among the students. It was recommended among others that parents should continue to get involved in their children's academic progress by monitoring their activities in and out of school, ensuring that home work is done, providing all necessary materials they need in school and meeting with their teachers when the need arises.

Key words: Mathematics, Anxiety, Computer-based, Paper-and-Pen examination

Introduction

The National Council for Teaching Mathematics (NCTM) addressed the need for all students to have access to learning and understanding of mathematics throughout their elementary, secondary and tertiary institutions and National policy on education (2014) opined that learners must develop mathematical skills even though many students find it difficult to learn mathematics (NCTM, 2000). Recently, there has been a trend in shifting the mode of assessment from paper pencil test (PPT) to computer based test (CBT) in the majority of educational institutions and this shift requires institutions to revise and renew their curricula methodology and pedagogy while taking the necessary practical changes for the successful implementation of this new assessment methodology into account (Chen, 2012; Genc, 2012; Hsiao, Tu, & Chung, 2012; OECD, 2010). Since it requires changes not only in the assessment methodology but also in the curricula methodology and pedagogy in educational institutions, substituting PBT with CBT is a major shift which raises serious questions regarding the rationale behind this rather radical change.

Use of CBT as a summative assessment tool carries concrete practical and economic benefits because it provides facility to test an immense number of student cohort with the facility of automated marking of responses (Charman, 1999; Zakrzewski & Bull, 1998). CBT is a mode of testing that acts as a catalyst for change, provides a base for change in mode of learning, instruction and curricula in educational institutions (Scheuermann & Pereira, 2008). Recently in most of the educational institutions there is a recent trend in shifting the mode of assessment from PPT to CBT. Administering the CBT mode of assessments is becoming predominantly widespread in educational assessment domain because this major variation in assessment methodology leads to practical changes in pedagogy and curricula methodology (Chen, 2012; Genc, 2012; Hsiao, Tu, & Chung, 2012; OECD, 2010). Pedagogical advantages on CBT include: providing a fast and error free feedback; repeatability of tests consisting of randomly-generated test items; unquestionable reliability and fairness; flexibility in allocation of test timing and venue; and, direct responsibility for one's own learning and test taking (Charman, 1999). Despite the importance and advantages of CBT many students have developed fear and anxiety while struggling to build a foundation necessary to find success and confidence when writing examination in mathematics classes. In order to build the high-quality mathematics programs outlined by the NCTM, teachers must address the issue of mathematics anxiety.

Anxiety is an unpleasant feeling characterized by fear or feeling of apprehension. It is evident when the person is worried and has some concern over an issue. It is one of the human emotions and is a feeling which all of us undergo at some point in our lives. It definitely affects our behaviour (Barlow & David 2000). Anxiety is a reaction to tension which is experienced by the learner. This reaction can be emotional or physical. Those students who are frequently experiencing these reactions can badly affect their memory and recall. The misinterpretation of information perceived can adversely affect performance. Anxiety was defined by (Asadullapoor, Fati & Gharaee, 2010) as feeling that is undesirable and unclear when a student's predicts danger. Anxiety is a common phenomenon that constitutes a universal cause student's poor academic performance. The academic performance which is very important to all stakeholders including students, their parents, and the institution, is adversely affected by anxiety (Barlow & David 2000).

Mathematics anxiety is inability of the learner to perform mathematics calculations, such as an ability by otherwise intelligent person to cope with quantification, and more generally, mathematics (Perry, 2004). According to Bursal and Paznokas (2006), mathematics anxiety is a state of discomfort that occurs in response to situations involving mathematical tasks that are threatening to self-esteem and the panic, helplessness, paralysis, and mental disorganization arising among some students when they are required to solve a mathematical problem. Oxford and Vordick (2006) added that mathematics anxiety as a disporting condition when students struggle with mathematics. Mathematics anxiety refers to a wide range of negative emotional responses related to mathematics and situations involving mathematics (Ashcraft & Ridley, 2005). Mathematics Anxiety has been defined as feelings of tension and anxiety which interfere with the

manipulation of numbers and solving Mathematical problems in open variety of social life and academic situation. Mathematics Anxiety defines is psychological feelings of tension (Richardson & Suinn, 1972).

Mathematics Anxiety considered as fear or phobia, dread which produce negative response specific to the Mathematics learning, Mathematics solving and mathematical activities that interferes with performance (Whyte, 2009). Mathematics Anxiety has been defined by Tobias and Weissbord (1980), as a panic, helpless, paralysis and mental disorganization among the students that appears at the time of solving the mathematical problem (Fiore, 1999). The formation of Mathematics Anxiety typically refers to the emotional and mental agony that occurs in some students while attempting to understand Mathematics (Wu, Amin, Malcarne & Menon, 2012). Mathematics Anxiety as a psychological; structure interferes in developing students' ability of thinking skill, it can be considered as a significantly important factor of low level of problem-solving skills of the school students in Mathematics (Das & Das, 2012). Jain and Downson (2009), define Mathematics anxiety as low self-confidence, fear, a negative mind set, less interest to manipulation of numbers and the solving the mathematical problem.

Mathematics anxiety can be manifested with some symptomatic characters by which we can identify that the learner is suffering from Mathematics Anxiety. There are physical, psychological and behavioural symptomatic characters. In physical symptoms, it is associated with the increasing of heart beat, clammy hands, appears light headiness and upset stomach. In psychological symptoms, it is associates with inability to provide concentration in Mathematics class, students feel helpless, and feeling of disgrace and worry. In Behavioral symptoms, it is united with avoidance of Mathematics classes, students' disfavour the Mathematics home work until the last moment and irregular study (Plaisance, 2009; Jackson, 2008; Woodard, 2004). Mathematics anxiety starts off at different ages for different learners, like that some students may involve with it as early as third or fourth grade (Jackson & Leffingwell, 1999). Again, as per Perina (2002), the problem of Mathematics anxiety is thought to occur in primary school (Perina, 2002). A student with Mathematics anxiety may have a bad attitude about Mathematics before attempting the problem or even before the teachers explain the problem. Mathematics anxiety students may be nervous and unable to sit till the end of the Mathematics class. Mathematics anxiety students may dread to attend in Mathematics class and fill greater fear of answering a teacher's question incorrectly in Mathematics class rather than other class (Hsiu-Zu, 2000). Mathematics Anxious students may feel embarrassed, frustrated, irritated and fearful (Buxton, 1981). Negative attitude about Mathematics can be expressed with facial expression, body language and other indicators. A student with Mathematics anxiety severely hinders his or her working memory (Perina, 2002). Mathematics Anxious student feels difficulty to solve a problem with long division as a reason he is unable to focus on performing the calculations, and also has to deal with negative thought towards Mathematics. Mathematics anxiety is not limited only the school subject but also it is inclined to that he has test and social anxiety as well (Perina, 2002).

There are many causes for Mathematics anxiety among the school students. Mathematics anxiety is caused by poor test result, negative classroom experience, lack of eagerness to complete difficult assignment, negative attitude towards the Mathematics learning among the parents and even teachers. The anxiety about Mathematics of parents and teachers pass to their children and students (Furner & Duffy, 2002). It becomes very difficult for students to like Mathematics when their parents already disliked and did not do well in Mathematics themselves as well as they do not think that it is important (Smith, 2004). In the study conducted by Newstead (1995), the most possible causes of Mathematics anxiety include teacher's anxiety, societal factors, educational and environmental factors, classroom experience, innate cognition of Mathematics, failure in school achievement test and class room punishment (Newstead, 1995). In school, assessment and evaluation system mainly high-stakes test can increase the tendency to develop negative attitude to the students' mind about Mathematics and enlarged the area of Mathematics anxiety (Scarpello, 2007). It is harder to learn Mathematics to the students due to lack of conceptual understanding the mathematical situation with computation skills. The real examples, memorized by writing rules and manipulation of symbols with little are harder to learn Mathematics rather than an integrated conceptual

understanding structure (Skemp, 1986). The result of test examination among the school students' can increase the tendency towards the Mathematics anxiety (Schoenfeld, 1988). Sometimes teacher provokes his students to dislike Mathematics. The Mathematics weakness has been perceived by the teacher but he is unwilling to give extra help to the students to solve the handedness. But the teacher may angry or upset when his teaching doesn't understand by his students, although his expectation has unrealistic from his students' and specially emphasis to covering the text book (Furner & Duffy, 2002). In Mathematics class the teacher needs to be creative in his teaching learning process (Pyne, Bates & Turner, 1995) but focuses the teaching approach of 'explain practice memorized' (Steele & Alfred, 1998) which grow up the Mathematics anxiety among the students. Sometimes the teacher can discourage the willingness to know about Mathematics of students and teacher dislike to give answer to the students' asking questions which are a sign of desire of learning (Jackson & Leffingwell, 1999).

Furthermore, the extant literature reported mixed results about the gender impact on the performance of the examinees. For example, Gallagher, Bridgeman, and Cahalan, (2000); and Leeson, (2006) asserted the existence of gender effect on examination mode. Also, Oduntan et al. (2015) concluded that male students outperformed female students on CBT, whereas Jalali, Zeinali, and Nobakht (2014) emphasized that female students outperformed male students in both modes. Furthermore, Wallace and Clariana (2005) found that male students outperformed their female peers on the initial assessment regardless of the test mode, whereas female students using CBT outperformed male students on the final assessment.

On the contrary, Alexander et al., (2001) noted no gender differences in performance of both test modes. In addition, several studies presented mixed findings of the performance of examinees from both genders based on their previous usage of computers. In addition, other studies stated that males were thought to be more positive towards computers than females concerning computer anxiety (Chou, 2003; Tsai, Lin, & Tsai, 2001), computer self-efficacy (Durndell & Thomson, 1997; Schaumburg, 2004) and computer attitude (Liaw, 2002). On the contrary, several studies found no significant differences in gender concerning computer anxiety, computer liking, and confidence about using computers (Clariana & Wallace, 2002; Francis, 1994), and perceived the use fullness of computers (Shashaani, 1997).

Guita and Tan (2018) carried out a research on Mathematics Anxiety and Students' Academic Achievement in a Reciprocal Learning Environment. The study determined the mathematics anxiety and students' academic achievement in a reciprocal learning environment. It sought to determine the level of achievement of students when exposed to reciprocal learning environment (RLE) and to those exposed to non-reciprocal learning environment (non-RLE). Results showed the level of students' anxiety towards mathematics is high anxiety before the treatment and becomes moderate after the intervention for both RLE and Non-RLE groups. Also, no significant difference in the mathematics anxiety of students was observed in both groups.

Eid's (2005) analysis of 5th grade females completing a math problem solving test on alternately administered CBTs and PPTs showed a statistically significant difference occurring between the two testing modes, favoring the CBT. Another study examined the mode effect of CBT and PPT on a multiple-choice test taken by students with ADHD (Lee, Osborne & Carpenter, 2010). A statistically significant difference was found favoring those students in the CBT condition. Likewise, Clariana and Wallace (2002) examined the posttest scores of students in a CBT or PPT condition on a 100-question multiple choice test. The results showed a statistically significant difference with a large effect size in favor of the computer test takers. These studies show an advantage for CBT

Ashcraft and Faust (1994) claim that higher MA scores observed in case of computerized administration are due to the fact that mathematics anxious learners do not feel comfortable with computers. Researchers have found significant differences in mathematics anxiety between computer-administered testing and traditional paper and pencil testing (Chuah, Drasgow & Roberts, 2006; Gosling, Vazire, Srivastava & John, (2004). These studies and articles attributed the differences to several factors. Russell

and Haney (1996) found significant differences in the performance of students on the National Assessment of Educational Progress computerized tests when compared to traditional paper and pencil tests. Bodmann and Robinson (2004) conducted an experimental study to compare speed and performances differences between computer-based (CBTs) and paper-pencil tests (PPTs). Results showed that undergraduates completed the CBT faster than PBT with no difference in scores. In fact, many research works have been conducted to evaluate the comparability of computer-based assessment and paper and pencil based assessment. Some studies revealed that there is a significant difference between the two testing modes on test scores (Scheuermann & Björnsson, 2009; Choi, Kim & Boo, 2003), while other studies reported opposite or inconsistent results (Al-Amri, 2009; Boo, 1997).

Statement of the Problem

The decline in performance in Mathematics by students has created anxiety in students and strengthens the perception that they are weak in mathematics. This response will ultimately be a belief that has to change. According to Hadfield and McNeil (1999), most students experience mathematics anxiety since elementary school. This fear is transferred by school teachers through teaching methods. Traditional methods such as lecturing; teaching basic skills without an emphasis on the concept has been identified as a factor that contribute to Mathematics anxiety. Research by Fulya (2008) has shown that Mathematics anxiety had become one of the factors contributing to the decline of the mathematical achievements of the students. The problem of this research work is tackling Mathematics anxiety among students.

Research questions

This study assesses mathematics anxiety levels among Earlychildhood Care Education pre-service teachers During Computer-Based Versus Paper-and-Pen Examination. The paper attempts to present the answers to the following research questions:

1. What is the level of mathematics anxiety among Earlychildhood Care Education pre-service teachers During Computer-Based Versus Paper-and-Pen Examination?
2. What are the factors that caused the mathematics anxiety among Earlychildhood Care Education pre-service teachers?

Method

This study adopted descriptive research design. The population of the study comprised of all 345 pre-service teachers in school of early childhood and primary education in Alvan Ikoku Federal College Education. The pre-service teachers were randomly selected in two groups. The group one comprise of 162 pre service teachers 300 level Regular Programme involving (80 males and 82 males) were administered the survey questionnaire comprising of MAI anxiety scale after computer-based examination whereas group two comprise 183 pre-service teachers 300 level Evening /Weekend Programme involving (89 males and 91 females) were administered MAI scale after paper and pen examination. The data collection was done during periods of the first semester. The Mathematics Anxiety Inventory (MAI) developed by Plake and Parker (1982) and adopted for use in this study. Only those pre service teachers who manifested the three symptoms (physical, psychological and behavioral) of mathematics anxiety during the first semester (June 2017-January 2018) were identified as subjects of this study (Le Moyne, 2003). The respondents answered the level of anxiety that they experience on the items in the test along five levels (Very High, High, Moderate, Low and Very Low) scored as 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The validity of the instrument was done by two experts from mathematics education and one from measurement and evaluation. A trial test was carried out on pre service teachers outside the sample for the study using cronbach alpha method; reliability co-efficient of 0.82 was established. For the data analysis, descriptive statistics including frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation and t-test were used.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of mathematics anxiety among Early Childhood Care Education pre-service teachers During Computer-Based Versus Paper-and-Pen Examination?

Table 1. Mean and Standard deviation on level of Mathematics Anxiety

Variables	Computer-based examination		Paper and pen examination	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Physical anxiety	2.57	1.8	2.42	1.4
Physiological	3.89	1.6	3.79	1.7
Behavioral	3.07	1.2	3.13	1.3

Results in table 1 shows that the level of mathematics anxiety among Early Childhood Care Education pre-service teachers during Computer-Based (Physical anxiety 2.57, Physiological 3.89 Behavioural 3.07) while Paper-and-Pen Examination (Physical anxiety 2.42, Physiological 3.79 Behavioural 3.13).

Research Question 2: What is the level of mathematics anxiety among male and female Early Childhood Care Education pre-service teachers During Computer-Based Versus Paper-and-Pen Examination?

Gender	Mean anxiety status					
	NUMBER	Computer-based Examination		Paper and pen Examination		
		Mean	SD	NUMBER	Mean	SD
Male	80	3.78	1.8	89	3.28	1.7
Female	82	3.92	1.6	91	3.47	1.5

Results in table 2 shows that the level of mathematics anxiety among male and female Early Childhood Care Education pre-service teachers During Computer-Based is (3.78 and 3.92) Paper-and-Pen Examination is 3.38 and 3.47).

Research Question 3: What are the factors that caused the mathematics anxiety among Early Childhood Care Education pre-service teachers?

Table 3 mean and standard deviation on factors on mathematics anxiety

S/n	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Lack of self confidence	3.67	1.3	Accepted
2	Interest and study habits	3.45	1.6	Accepted
3	Teacher factor	3.73	1.5	Accepted
4	Fear of failure	3.35	1.1	Accepted
5	Pressure from parents and peers	3.56	1.2	Accepted
6	Poor skills in analysis	3.23	1.0	Accepted
7	Abstract mathematics concepts	3.78	1.5	Accepted
8	classroom experience	3.19	1.0	Accepted
9	Innate cognition of mathematics	3.45	1.6	Accepted

Results in table 3 shows that all the items scored above 2.50. This implies that Lack of self confidence, Interest and study habits, Teacher factor, Fear of failure Pressure from parents and peers, Poor skills in analysis and Abstract mathematics concepts are the factors that caused the mathematics anxiety among early childhood Care Education pre-service teachers.

Discussion

Results in table 1 indicated that there is high level of mathematics anxiety among Early Childhood Care Education pre-service teachers During Computer-Based than the Paper-and-Pen Examination. There

is result is in accord with the finding of studies (Chuah, Drasgow & Roberts, 2006; Gosling, Vazire, Srivastava & John, 2004) found significant differences in mathematics anxiety between computer-administered testing and traditional paper and pencil testing. Other studies revealed that there is a significant difference between the two testing modes on test scores (Scheuermann & Björnsson, 2009; Choi, Kim & Boo, 2003).

Also the result indicated that there is high level of mathematics anxiety among male and female Early Childhood Care Education pre-service teachers During Computer-Based than Paper-and-Pen Examination. This contradicts the findings of Bodmann and Robinson (2004) conducted an experimental study to compare speed and performances differences between computer-based (CBTs) and paper-pencil tests (PPTs). Both CBTs and PPTs contained 30 MCQs items with 35 minute of time limit. Approximately half the class (i.e. 28 students) took the first test on the computer and the rest preferred first test on paper. Procedures shifted for the second tests, with the first group receiving PPTs and second group received CBTs after two weeks. It was concluded that undergraduates completed the CBT faster than PBT with no difference in scores and gender.

Finally, the results indicated that, there are several factors that cause mathematics anxiety among early childhood Care Education pre-service teachers. There is results in line the finding of Newstead (1995), the most possible causes of Mathematics anxiety include teacher's anxiety, societal factors, educational and environmental factors, classroom experience, innate cognition of Mathematics, failure in school achievement test and class room punishment.

Conclusion

The study concludes that there is high level of mathematics anxiety among Early Childhood Care Education pre-service teachers During Computer-Based than the Paper-and-Pen Examination and there are several factors that cause mathematics anxiety among the students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and discussion made above, the researchers recommend as follows:

1. Parents should continue to get involved in their children's academic progress by monitoring their activities in and out of school, ensuring that home work is done, providing all necessary materials they need in school and meeting with their teachers when the need arises.
2. Mathematics teacher could enhance the students' attitude towards math through effective teaching strategies.
3. . Parents must continue to inspire, guide, and encourage their children to establish reading and study habits for Mathematics.
4. It is highly recommended that the teachers should continue pursue further studies for professional growth in order to become more effective and efficient especially those in the field of Mathematics.
5. Mathematics teachers should teach students' study habits, raise student's confidence in their mathematical abilities and provide more hands on activities during mathematics class.
6. . Mathematics teachers should be trained to address anxiety problems of individual student.
7. An Anxiety rating scale exam must be conducted every semester by Math teachers to determine and monitor the anxiety of the students.

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